

Crop management

Low-tillage broadcast rice productivity

Zhao Luman, Hunan Soil and Fertilizer Research Institute, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changsha, China

Rice - rice - green manure is a primary cropping pattern in Hunan Province. In general, a field must be plowed and harrowed several times a year. That destroys the soil structure, results in poorer soil aeration, demands more labor, and risks seedling damage from low temperature in May or high temperature in Jul.

Table 2. Rice benefits from 2 cultivation methods. Changsha, China, 1986.

Treatment	Rice season	Yield (t/ha)	Output value ^a (\$/ha)	Cost (\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)	Income increase (%)	Labor days/ha	Income/labor day (\$)	Income increase (%)
Low tillage, broadcast	Apr - Oct	13.9	1450.46	535.93	914.87	30.16	233	3.94	90
Transplanted	Apr - Oct	11.8	1235.19	532.30	702.89	—	339	2.07	—
Low tillage, broadcast	Jun - Oct	8.5	885.12	261.20	623.92	30.76	120	5.20	96
Transplanted	Jun - Oct	7.3	760.76	283.62	477.14	—	180	2.65	—

^aRice price US\$104.50/t (local government price). Exchange rate: US\$100 = 371.27 yuan RMB.

To maintain soil productivity and high rice yields, we developed a minimum tillage and broadcast sowing rice cultivation method. Experiments to study the economic benefits and effects on soil structure between the new

method and conventional transplanting began in 1983.

Our results show that the new method has a significant effect on rice yield and economic return (Table 1, 2). □

Table 1. Rice yield from 2 cultivation methods. Changsha, China, 1984-87.

Location	Cropping pattern	Season	Rice variety	Yield (t/ha)		Yield increase (%)
				Low tillage broadcast	Transplanted	
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr ^a - Jul	1984 Zhefur 802	6.8	5.9	15.2
Nan County	Fallow - rice	Apr - Jul	78-1000	7.3	6.0	22
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1985 Xiangzhao xieng 3	6.2	5.8	7
Changsha	Green manure - rice - rice	Apr ^b - Oct	Zhefu 802-V35	14.4	13.8	5
Nan County	Green manure - rice - rice	Apr - Oct	Zhaoyun fong-V35	13.7	12.3	11
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1986 2106	5.6	5.4	4
Changsha	Green manure - rice	Apr - Jul	1987 V35	6.3	4.8	32
Changsha	Barley - rice	Apr - Jul	V35	6.6	6.2	5

^aOne crop season. ^bTwo crop seasons.

Disease management

Host plants of rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses

A. Anjaneyulu, R. D. Daquioag, Ma. E. Mesina, H. Hibino, H. T. Lubigan, and K. Moody, IRRRI

In previous studies on RTV hosts, inoculated weed plants were indexed on the basis of infection and by testing

transmission of infection from weeds to rice by the vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Results were contradictory.

This study had two treatments. In the first, young seedlings of 5 *Oryza* spp. and 19 weed species were inoculated separately by exposing each seedling for 1 d to 10 GLH that had fed for 4 d on plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform (RTRV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses. In the second treatment, seedlings of 4 *Oryza* spp. and 19 weed species were inoculated with

GLH that had fed on RTSV-infected plants.

At 30 d after inoculation, plants were indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV. Extracts of inoculated plants having absorbance at 405 nm 3 times higher than that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain virus.

When seedlings were inoculated by GLH that had fed on plants infected with RTBV and RTSV, all *Oryza* spp. except *O. latifolia* were infected with RTBV and RTSV (Table 1). All doubly

Table 1. Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with RTBV and/or RTSV after inoculation by RTBV + RTSV viruliferous GLH. IRRI.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	RTBV		Infected plants (no.)	RTSV	
			Absorbance at 405 nm			Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants		Infected plants	Uninoculated plants
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>							
Acc. 100882	8	4	0.98-1.95	0.00	0	–	0.00
Acc. 101397	12	2	1.20-1.51	0.18	1	0.07	0.00
Acc. 101144	7	4	0.50-1.48	0.00	0	–	0.00
<i>O. barthii</i>							
Acc. 100122	8	8	0.20-0.44	0.00	8	0.48-1.39	0.00
Acc. 100921	5	5	0.15-0.40	0.00	3	1.01-1.11	0.02
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	2	0.25-0.48	0.00	0	–	0.02
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	10	9	0.57-1.51	0.14	4	0.34-0.89	0.00
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	12	0	–	0.01	5	0.18-0.46	0.00
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	8	0	–	0.02	4	0.06-0.06	0.00
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	9	1	0.20	0.05	1	0.36	0.00
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	12	3	0.04-0.14	0.01	0	–	0.00
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	12	8	0.11-1.47	0.00	1	0.36	0.00
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	10	2	0.14-0.17	0.04	0	–	0.00
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	12	1	0.33	0.10	0	–	0.11

Table 2. Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with RTSV after inoculation by RTSV-viruliferous GLH. IRRI.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 101144	7	5	0.11-0.29	0.03
Acc. 101397	12	3	0.09-0.14	0.02
<i>O. barthii</i>				
Acc. 100117	3	3	0.89-1.11	0.05
<i>O. longistaminata</i>				
Acc. 101196	9	4	0.12-1.82	0.03
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	20	3	0.05-0.09	0.01
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	22	10	0.07-0.15	0.02
<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i>	8	1	0.08	0.00
<i>C. difformis</i>	10	5	0.13-0.54	0.04
<i>C. rotundus</i>	12	6	0.04-0.45	0.01
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	10	5	0.10-0.15	0.00
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	12	3	0.34-0.40	0.10
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	12	4	0.04-0.12	0.01
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i>	10	5	0.18-0.37	0.05
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	12	5	0.10-0.35	0.00
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	10	4	0.36-0.43	0.10
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	10	2	0.05-0.07	0.00
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	11	2	0.13-0.16	0.02

infected plants showed symptoms typical of RTV. *O. australiensis* and *O. latifolia* were predominantly infected with RTBV.

Among weed species tested, only *Cyperus rotundus* and *Fimbristylis miliacea* were infected with RTBV and RTSV. The doubly infected *F. miliacea* plants showed stunting and discoloration of newly emerged leaves,

the *C. rotundus* plants did not. *Brachiaria mutica* and *Axonopus compressus* were infected with only RTSV; many other species were infected predominantly with RTBV.

Weeds not infected with either virus were *Brachiaria distachya*, *Chloris barbata*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Eragrostis*

tenella, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, and *Paspalum dilatatum*.

Among seedlings inoculated by GLH that had fed on RTSV-infected plants, 3 of 4 *Oryza* spp. and 13 of 19 weed species were infected with RTSV (Table 2). None of the infected plants showed symptoms. Species not infected with RTSV were *O. latifolia*, *Axonopus compressus*, *Brachiaria distachya*, *Chloris barbata*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Unrecorded weed hosts for *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in India

N. I. Singh and Kh. U. Singh, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba, Imphal 795001, India

Many rice pathogens are reported to survive on wild weed hosts. Weeds such as *Leersia hexandra*, *Panicum repens*, *Arundo donax*, *Brachiaria mutica*, and *Cyperus compressus* have been reported to harbor *P. oryzae* in India.

In 1986-87, we studied possible weed hosts for the rice blast fungus *P. oryzae* in ricefields and on rice bunds. Diseased weeds collected from rice-growing areas in Imphal, Thaubal, Bishenpur, Churachandpur, and Senapati districts were brought to the laboratory and the fungus isolated on potato dextrose agar (PDA). Pathogenicity of fungus isolates was tested by spraying mycelial fragments prepared from 7-d-old culture onto each weed host and control plant.

Reaction of different isolates of *P. oryzae* on weeds. Manipur, India.

Weed host	Isolate no.	Disease reaction ^a on	
		HR12	KD2-6-3
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	1	+	+
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	2	+	+
<i>C. compressus</i>	3	+	–
<i>C. iria</i>	4	+	+

^a+ = infection, – = no infection.